

GREEN DEVELOPMENT, GREEN ECONOMY AND GREEN GROWTH

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Abstract. In the article, the development, growth and features of the green economy were studied by the author, and proposals and recommendations were developed.

Keywords: green economy, business, development, world economy

Since the concept of a green economy involves the development of new indicators of sustainable development that would complement the GDP indicator, during the transition period, the concept of green growth is used to track the extent to which the economy of a particular region is moving towards a green economy.

The OECD developed and introduced the concept of green growth, defining it as maximizing economic growth and development without affecting the quantity and quality of natural assets and taking advantage of the growth potential that arises in the transition to a green economy. In general terms, green growth is GDP growth that is subject to green conditions and emphasizes green sectors as new engines of growth.

The emphasis on green sectors implies a change in the structure of the economy that:

- pays more attention to the social aspect of sustainable development (social cohesion, objectivity of several generations, ensuring access to a range of resources, combating poverty and unemployment);
- based not only on the processing sector, but increasingly based on the extractive sector and the service sector;

- prevails through environmentally friendly investment, production, trade, distribution and consumption, as well as the improvement of goods and services from an environmental point of view;
- leads to the use of natural resources on a sustainable basis, not dependent on fossil fuels;
- creates new economic opportunities, expanding the scope of economic development and reducing poverty;
- is an “ecological work system” in agriculture, industry, research and development, administration and services, which means performing work that will contribute to:
 - conservation of ecosystems and biodiversity;
 - reducing energy, resource and water consumption through highly effective strategies;
 - reducing carbon emissions;
 - minimizing or generally preventing the generation of all forms of waste and pollution.

Following the industrial and information revolutions, the “green economy revolution” is another catalyst that has the potential to transform the global economy. There are 3 main areas of financing green spending:

1. Energy efficiency – financing energy savings in buildings; vehicles with economical fuel consumption; public transport and railways; improvement of power lines.
2. Low carbon energy – financing the development of renewable energy sources (geothermal energy, hydroelectric power, wind and solar energy), nuclear power and CO₂ reduction.
3. Water, waste and pollution control – financing the management and control of water resources and waste levels, including water protection, water purification and water supply.

In other words, the global crisis has prompted states to look at the economic crisis differently and begin the process of transition to a low-carbon green economy.

Comprehensive economic stimulus measures, which are used in many countries, are aimed at greening the economy through direct government financing of public transport, energy efficiency, alternative forms of energy, water supply and sanitation, and pollution control.

The Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (ESCAP), whose members from the post-Soviet countries are Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Russia, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan, played a major role in promoting the concept of a green economy. At the initiative of ESCAP, a green growth strategy was adopted in 2005, which initially included 4 priority areas: sustainable consumption and production models; "greening" of enterprises and markets; sustainable infrastructure and green tax and budget reforms. Subsequently, 2 more areas were added - investing in natural capital and environmental performance indicators.

The Republic of Korea was the first country to declare green growth as a national strategy. The strategy focuses on three elements: industry, energy and investment. The strategy is aimed at maintaining the scale of industrial economic activity with minimal use of energy and other resources; minimizing the environmental pressures of all types of energy and resources used and taking steps to turn environmental investment into a driver of economic growth.

Many countries are using various green economy instruments in their national policies and development strategies. The need for green growth is increasingly being talked about in Russia, including at a high political level. However, many developing countries fear that the use of a green economy model could slow down their development process. This issue requires further analysis

and debate about the extent to which this is true and how possible costs can be reduced.

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